

Multiple Pin Fixation for Displaced Femoral Neck Fraction in Children

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Abstract

Femoral neck fractures in children are serious injuries due to their potential complications which may lead to a lifelong disability. We reviewed the results in ten consecutive patients less than 16 years old who were treated by open reduction and internal fixation with multiple Dunham's pins at Samawa general hospital from 1997 to 2002. There were six male and four female patients, and they ranged in age from six to fifteen years old. All patients sustained fracture in high velocity trauma. Six patients had transcervical fractures, three cervicotrochanteric and one intertrochanteric fracture. All fractures united satisfactorily within four months and there was one case of wound infection. Avascular necrosis of femoral head developed in one patient (10%), it was asymptomatic and healed spontaneously after two years on restriction of activities.

Keywords: Femoral neck fracture, lifelong disability, childhood, high velocity trauma, musculoskeletal injury.

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Introduction

Fractures of the femoral neck in childhood and adolescence are a rare accident injury (accounting for less than 1% of all fractures) [13]. Despite their rarity they are significant for the individual child because of the probability of complication reported in up to 60% of cases in the literatures [1,2,13]. In children fractures of the femoral neck most often are the results of high velocity trauma and so they are often associated with injury to head, chest or abdomen as well as other musculoskeletal injuries [14]. The priority in the treatment must be given first to life threatening injuries and then to the musculoskeletal injuries [14]. The late complications of femoral neck fractures (non-union, coxa vara, avascular necrosis of femoral head) in children are caused in one hand by direct damage to the growth plate and on the other by damage resulting from a circulation disorder [13]. The patient's age, localization of the fracture and the extent of displacement have a major impact on the prognosis [13].

Most authors advocate emergency surgical treatment [3,4,5,6] to relieve the haemarthrosis though according to the review by Niethard (1982) surgical treatment was not shown to be superior [2,13].

Varus and non-union are affected by treatment, reports on children with femoral neck fracture have emphasized the importance of implication or

compression for minimizing the risk of non-union and not only the various devices used for internal fixation [4,14].

Avascular necrosis of femoral head appears to be related to the severity of initial injury and unaffected by treatment [3,6].

The childhood femoral head also has a strong potential for revascularization and complete reconstruction of the necrotic bone [8,15].

Materials and Methods

From April 1997 to April 2002, ten children with displaced fracture of femoral neck were treated by open reduction and internal fixation in samawa General hospital (Table 1). The mean age was ten years (range six to fifteen years). Six were boys and four were girls. All patients were involved in a high velocity trauma; seven were injured in a motor vehicle accident, the remaining three were injured in a fall of more than 4 meters [14]. Significant injuries to other parts of the body were recorded in six patients. There were six transcervical three cervicotrochanteric and one intertrochanteric fractures, all were displaced fractures. Six patients were treated within three days after injury and the other four had delayed treatment (more than three but less than one week) due to delayed referral to our trauma center.

Table 1: Patient with displaced femoral neck fractures

case	Age(yr)	Sex	Type of fracture	Interval between Injury and Fixation (days)	Associated injury
1	13	F	Transcervical	3	Facial wound
2	7	M	Cervicotrochanteric	2	
3	9	M	Transcervical	4	Fractural humerus

4	15	M	Cervicotrochanteric	2	
5	11	F	Transcervical	5	Back trauma
6	10	M	Transcervical	4	
7	12	M	Intertrochanteric	4	Ankle trauma
8	10	F	Transcervical	3	
9	9	M	Cervicotrochanteric	5	Juvenile colles
10	6	F	Transcervical	3	Scalp wound

Figure 1: Information about the patients' gender, associated injuries and types of fractures

Operative Procedure

The patient was placed on the fracture table in the supine position through the standard Watson-Jones approach the fracture was exposed. Intracapsular haematoma was evacuated by anterior capsulotomy. open reduction of the fracture was performed. The fracture

was fixed internally with four Dunham's pins inserted parallel to the axis of the femoral neck (anterosuperior, anteroinferior, posterosuperior and postero inferior) to avoid loss of reduction due to excessive compression of the posterior part of the femoral neck, which is frequently comminuted (see Figure 2) [14].

Figure 2: Classification of femoral neck fractures in children (Delbert classification): a) transepiphyseal; b) transcervical; c) cervicotrochanteric; d) intertrochanteric

The mean operative time for fixation of the femoral neck fracture was 90 minutes [14]. Blood transfusion was always needed. Patients were given antibiotics (Cephalosporin) pre-operatively, perioperatively and for five days postoperatively [14].

Postoperative immobilisation using unilateral hip spica for 3 weeks was used in six patients (those with transcervical fractures). All patients were hospitalized for two weeks.

Results

All fractures showed satisfactory union within 2-3 months except in case No. (5) where there was delay in union for 5months due to wound infection.

Full weight bearing was allowed three to five months following surgery. No epiphyseal growth arrest or coxa vara was recorded, one patient developed superficial wound infection. Segmental avascular necrosis occurred in one patient case No. (5) it was asymptomatic. Complete healing occurred two years later without residual ill effect.

Initial leg length discrepancy was seen in six patients (four longer limbs, two shorter limbs) but was corrected Spontaneously within two years in all affected case

Range of hip movements returned to normal in all patients in three patients; There was initial limitation of the movement, which persisted for about one year and was treated successfully by physiotherapy.

Flexion, abduction and external rotation movements were the most affected. Residual limitation of degrees of rotation to less than 10 degrees was regard acceptable. The pins were remove one year later in all patients after complete bone union

Discussion

Femoral neck fractures in children are rare injuries accounting for less than 1% of all fractures [1,2]. They are serious injuries because their complications may lead to a lifelong disability [5,6,8,16].

All fractures in this series resulted from high velocity trauma. Early open reduction and rigid internal fixation of the fracture remains the treatment of choice in the majority of displaced fractures in children. In our study,

all fractures were fixed by four Dunham's pins (3.5mm). Varus and non-union are affected by the treatment. Vascular compromise with necrosis or growth problems are not related to therapy and hardly to Control [9,10,16].

We attribute the absence of non-union and low (10%) incidence of radiographic incidence of aseptic necrosis in our series to our protocol of early reduction and internal fixation with compression [14].

The natural history of avascular necrosis of the femoral head in necrosis of the children shows significant differences as compared to adults. Depending on the remaining growth potential, even extensive damage of the femoral head can regenerate, as long as epiphyseal growth plate is not involved in the process, otherwise the deformity will increase with time[8].

This may explain the full recovery of aseptic necrosis in case number five. who sustained the fracture when she was 11 years old and who showed full clinical and radiographic recovery of the femoral head two years later.

Although our series was too small to permit individual assessment of the effect of early fixation, capsulotomy and optimum reduction, our belief is that all these three factors were the keystone to attain our results which when compared to other series seems to be out-standing [4,5,8,11,12,14].

The smooth pointed ends of Dunham's pins have minimal risk of injuring the growth plate or impairing the blood supply to femoral head.

Other fixation devices that used by other authors for fixation of femoral neck fractures such as cancellous screws, triflanged or other nails be avoided because of the potential of damaging the blood supply to femoral head by the blows of the mallet [12,14].

Conclusions

Femoral neck fractures in children are rare injuries. Early open reduction and Rigid internal fixation of displaced femoral neck fractures is highly useful method of treatment in absence of image intensifier facility. Union of fracture can be affected by meticulous and rigid fixation of the fracture, whereas the complication of avascular necrosis of femoral head implies vascular compromise at time of accident is not related to therapy and can hardly be prevented.

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